

MMZ

Figure 4A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4A

2sec (Exposure time)

Lane 1: Sib-1 Clone-1, Lane 2: Sib-1 Clone 2, Lane 3: I-ASD Clone 1, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 Clone 2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4A: GAPDH for PS6 Film

Figure 4A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4A

Lane 1: Sib-1 Clone-1, Lane 2: Sib-1 Clone 2, Lane 3: I-ASD Clone 1, **Lane 4: I-ASD-1 Clone 2**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 4A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4A

Lane 1: Sib-1 Clone-1, Lane 2: Sib-1 Clone 2, Lane 3: I-ASD Clone 1, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 Clone 2

total
S6 7122

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

FUJIFILM SAFETY

Figure 4A: GAPDH for Total S6 Film

Crab
GAPDH

✓
Good

Figure 4A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4A

GAPDH (35 kD)

Lane 1: Sib-1 Clone-1, Lane 2: Sib-1 Clone 2, Lane 3: I-ASD Clone 1, Lane 4: I-ASD-1 Clone 2

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows